

Adaptive Low-Rank Product Transformers with Dynamic Expert Routing for Online Continual Learning*

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Abstract

Inspired by the role of sleep in biological continual learning, we introduce RVW, a transformer architecture for online continual adaptation of pretrained models. RVW maintains a small pool of per-layer experts that grow and are pruned in response to distribution shift, with no replay buffer and no explicit task identifier. Applied to TinyLlama-1.1B on a 15,000-chunk six-domain stream, RVW reaches 40 average held-out PPL, substantially better than EWC (158), fine-tuning (164), and LoRA (448) on the same parameter-matched base, while preserving prior-domain performance. Threshold sweeps suggest that learned knowledge is encoded in the routing combination of experts across layers rather than individual experts specializing on specific domains.

1 Introduction

A pretrained transformer fixed at the end of training cannot adapt to distributions it never saw, and unrestricted continued training overwrites prior knowledge. We are interested in *online* adaptation of such models—a streaming setting where the model must improve on whatever distribution arrives next without storing replay buffers and without forgetting earlier distributions. We introduce RVW, a transformer architecture whose FFN and attention projections each support a small pool of low-rank “expert” chains that are dynamically grown and pruned during adaptation in response to distribution shift. The low-rank factorization is not the contribution: it is the enabling substrate that lets a pool of K cloned experts fit in roughly the parameter budget of a single dense projection, where a dense formulation would multiply parameters by K .

The biological motivation. Biological neural systems acquire new knowledge continually without catastrophically overwriting the old, and they appear to do so through an interleaving of two complementary phases. *Waking plasticity* forms new synaptic connections in response to novel stimuli; *sleep consolidation* selectively prunes weak connections while retaining and potentiating those that proved useful [15]. The interaction—not just the individual phases—is what makes stable acquisition of new knowledge compatible with retention of prior learning. Most continual-learning methods in deep learning operate in only one of these regimes. Regularization-based approaches (EWC [6], SI [16]) penalize weight movement during continued training but do not add new capacity for genuinely novel distributions; progressive-expansion approaches [11] add capacity for each new task but lack a corresponding consolidation mechanism that bounds growth or removes unhelpful additions. Replay-based methods [2] can sit between these but require explicit storage of past experience that biological systems do not maintain.

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The clone/prune lifecycle as a sleep–wake analog. The mechanism introduced in this paper is structurally analogous to the sleep–wake cycle. A novelty signal—a sharp loss spike, or in later sections a per-layer gradient spike—triggers cloning of an existing factor-chain expert. The new expert is displaced along the steepest-descent direction at the moment of cloning, so that it arrives partly pre-adapted to the distribution that triggered the spike. This is the analog of waking plasticity: a new connection forms in response to the stimulus, with its initial direction shaped by the stimulus itself. Pruning runs on a fixed cadence and removes experts whose recent usage falls below a threshold; only experts that proved useful survive successive prune cycles. This is the analog of sleep consolidation. Combined with low-rank product factorization—which provides parameter efficiency and a structural decoupling of shared projection bottlenecks from per-expert content—the result is a transformer that adapts online to distribution shift without storing replay data and without catastrophically forgetting prior distributions. We call this model **RVW**. Our contributions develop this mechanism through a progression of scales and tasks.

Our contributions:

- A **low-rank product layer** that replaces each dense projection with shared $P_{\text{down}}/P_{\text{up}}$ projections and a chain of small orthogonally-initialized factors with RMSNorm stabilization. The factorization enables a pool of cloned experts to share the heavy projections and differ only in the small bottleneck factor chain, keeping the active-parameter budget close to that of a single dense projection.
- An **adaptive expert pool** with window-level routing, per-layer gradient-norm clone triggering, and usage-based pruning—requiring no learned gating beyond a per-expert key vector.
- **Gradient-directed clone perturbation:** initializing new experts one step in the descent direction, enabling aggressive perturbation scales that pre-adapt clones toward the triggering distribution.
- **SVD-based decomposition of pretrained models:** applying the factorization to TinyLlama-1.1B via truncated SVD of SwiGLU FFN layers (gate, up, down projections) and attention Q/K/V/O projections, with brief recovery fine-tuning to close the approximation gap.
- **Null-logit routing:** appending a fixed-zero logit to the softmax routing to ensure gradient flow for single-expert layers, unifying the clone-triggering mechanism across all layer types regardless of current expert count.
- An empirical evaluation on a 6-domain online-adaptation stream over the decomposed TinyLlama-1.1B base, with comparisons to fine-tuning, EWC, and LoRA on both the decomposed and the uncompressed model.

2 Related Work

Low-rank and factored weight matrices. Low-rank decomposition of neural network weights has a long history, from early compression work to modern parameter-efficient fine-tuning. LoRA [5] freezes pre-trained weights and adds trainable low-rank update matrices $\Delta W = BA$; our approach differs by replacing the *entire* weight with a product of small factors rather than adding a low-rank correction. Kronecker-factored layers [14] and tensor decompositions [10] pursue similar compression goals but with different factorization structures. Our product chain $P_{\text{up}} \cdot M_L \cdots M_1 \cdot P_{\text{down}}$ with intermediate RMSNorm is closest to deep linear networks with normalization, which have been studied for their optimization properties [12].

Mixture-of-experts. Sparse mixture-of-experts (MoE) models route tokens to a subset of expert subnetworks [13, 3, 7]. Standard MoE uses a learned gating network for per-token routing; we instead use coarse window-level routing with a simple dot-product key lookup, which we find more effective for domain-level adaptation than per-token dispatch (§3.3). Our clone/prune lifecycle dynamically adjusts expert count, whereas most MoE architectures fix the number of experts at initialization.

Continual and online learning. Catastrophic forgetting in continual learning is addressed by regularization (EWC [6], SI [16]), replay buffers [2], progressive expansion [11], and parameter isolation [8]. Our clone/prune mechanism is a form of progressive expansion—new experts are added when loss spikes detect distribution shift—but unlike Progressive Neural Networks, old experts can be pruned to bound capacity. The loss-threshold trigger relates to surprise-based modulation in Bayesian online learning [1].

Meta-learning and fast adaptation. MAML [4] and Reptile [9] learn initializations that enable few-shot adaptation via gradient descent. Our gradient-directed clone perturbation shares a conceptual link: at clone time, the new expert is initialized one gradient step in the descent direction, pre-adapting it toward the current loss surface. However, we do not meta-learn this initialization—the gradient is computed from the current batch, not across a task distribution.

3 Architecture

3.1 Low-Rank Product Layer

A standard FFN computes $\text{FFN}(x) = W_2 \sigma(W_1 x)$ where $W_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{ff} \times d}$ and $W_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_{ff}}$. We replace each dense matrix with:

$$W \approx P_{\text{up}} \cdot M_L \cdot \text{RMSNorm} \cdot M_{L-1} \cdots \text{RMSNorm} \cdot M_1 \cdot P_{\text{down}} \quad (1)$$

where $P_{\text{down}} \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times d_{\text{in}}}$ and $P_{\text{up}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{out}} \times r}$ are shared projection matrices, and each $M_i \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$ is initialized orthogonally. RMSNorm layers between factors prevent gradient magnitude drift through the chain.

The point of this factorization, in the context of clone/prune, is that the heavy parameters live in P_{down} and P_{up} ($\mathcal{O}(d \cdot r)$ each, with d on the order of thousands at scale) while the per-expert factor chain is $L \cdot r^2$ ($\mathcal{O}(r^2)$, with r on the order of hundreds). A pool of K experts that share the projections and differ only in the factor chain therefore costs $2dr + KLr^2$ parameters versus $K \cdot d_{\text{in}} \cdot d_{\text{out}}$ for K independent dense projections—a $\sim K(d/r)$ -fold reduction in expert-pool parameters. At TinyLlama scale ($d_{\text{in}} = d_{\text{out}} = 2048$, $r = 256$, $L = 3$), per-expert cost is $\sim 200\text{K}$ parameters against $\sim 4.2\text{M}$ for a dense duplicate. Without this factorization the clone/prune mechanism described next would be infeasible at realistic model scales.

3.2 Routed Low-Rank FFN

Multiple expert factor chains share the same P_{down} and P_{up} projections. A small router network (2-layer MLP) produces per-token routing weights via Gumbel-softmax:

$$w = \text{GumbelSoftmax}(\text{Router}(x), \tau) \quad (2)$$

The output is a weighted combination over experts. Temperature τ is annealed during training, optionally with a warmup period. A Switch Transformer-style auxiliary loss encourages load balancing:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{aux}} = N \sum_{s=1}^N f_s \cdot p_s \quad (3)$$

where f_s is the (non-differentiable) fraction of tokens assigned to expert s and p_s is the mean routing probability.

3.3 Adaptive Low-Rank FFN with Window Routing

The adaptive variant replaces per-token Gumbel-softmax routing with coarse-grained **window-level routing**. For a window of W consecutive tokens, the mean hidden state \bar{h} selects an expert via dot-product similarity with learned key vectors:

$$\text{logits}_s = \bar{h} \cdot k_s, \quad s^* = \arg \max_s \text{logits}_s \quad (4)$$

During training, Gumbel-softmax with `hard=True` is used; at inference, `hard argmax`. The model starts with a single expert (copied from a pre-trained low-rank model) and dynamically adjusts capacity:

- **Cloning:** With fixed probability p_{clone} per step, a random active expert is copied to an empty slot with small Gaussian noise ($\sigma = 0.01$) added to factors and keys.
- **Pruning:** Every T_{prune} steps, experts with usage fraction below a threshold θ are deactivated, freeing slots for future clones.

This creates an evolutionary dynamic: new experts are born as noisy copies of successful ones, then either find a niche (sustained usage) or are pruned. Figure 1 shows the resulting layer structure: shared $P_{\text{down}}/P_{\text{up}}$ projections, a per-expert factor chain in the rank- r bottleneck, and a window-level router whose dot-product against per-expert keys produces the routing weights w_s .

Algorithm 1 Online Adaptation with Clone/Prune

- 1: **Input:** Pre-trained model \mathcal{M} , stream $\{(x_t, y_t)\}$
 - 2: Convert \mathcal{M} to adaptive (single expert per layer)
 - 3: **for** each batch (x_t, y_t) in stream **do**
 - 4: Forward pass with window routing
 - 5: Backprop and update parameters
 - 6: With probability p_{clone} : clone random expert
 - 7: **if** $t \bmod T_{\text{prune}} = 0$ **then**
 - 8: Prune experts with usage $< \theta$
 - 9: Reset usage counters
 - 10: **end if**
 - 11: **end for**
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3.4 SVD Decomposition of Pretrained Models

The from-scratch experiments trained low-rank product models from scratch. To validate the approach on pretrained knowledge, we decompose an existing model—TinyLlama-1.1B [17]—via truncated SVD.

TinyLlama uses SwiGLU activation in its FFN layers, computing:

$$\text{FFN}(x) = W_{\text{down}}(\text{SiLU}(W_{\text{gate}}x) \odot W_{\text{up}}x) \quad (5)$$

where $W_{\text{gate}}, W_{\text{up}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{ff}} \times d}$ and $W_{\text{down}} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d_{\text{ff}}}$, with $d = 2048$ and $d_{\text{ff}} = 5632$. Each of the three projection matrices is decomposed independently via truncated SVD:

$$W = U_r S_r V_r^\top \approx \underbrace{(U_r \sqrt{S_r})}_{P_{\text{up}}} \cdot \underbrace{M_L \cdot \text{RMSNorm} \cdots M_1}_{\text{identity chain}} \cdot \underbrace{(\sqrt{S_r} V_r^\top)}_{P_{\text{down}}} \quad (6)$$

Figure 1: Adaptive low-rank product layer. The dense weight W of one projection is factored as $P_{\text{up}} \cdot M_L \cdot N \cdots N \cdot M_1 \cdot P_{\text{down}}$, where $P_{\text{down}}: \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{in}}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^r$ and $P_{\text{up}}: \mathbb{R}^r \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{d_{\text{out}}}$ are shared across all K experts (gray) and the per-expert factor chain $M_L \cdot N \cdots N \cdot M_1$ lives in the rank- r bottleneck (blue, with RMSNorm in yellow). At each window, the router (red, bottom) computes the mean hidden state \bar{h} , scores it against per-expert key vectors k_s , and applies the resulting routing weights w_s to the weighted sum of expert outputs. Cloning duplicates one expert’s factor chain (and key vector) into an empty slot with a small perturbation; pruning deactivates slots whose recent usage falls below threshold. The shared projections are not affected by clone/prune; only the per-expert factor-chain content and the router keys are.

The singular values are split symmetrically ($\sqrt{S_r}$ absorbed into both projections), and the factor chain $M_1 \dots M_L$ is initialized to identity matrices. RMSNorm layers between factors introduce a small distortion from true identity, so a brief recovery fine-tune on WikiText-103 closes the approximation gap.

At rank $r = 256$ with $L = 3$ factors, each FFN layer compresses from 34.6M to 6.5M parameters ($5.3\times$). Across all 22 layers, total FFN parameters drop from 761M to 143M. With attention parameters unchanged, the full model shrinks from $\sim 1.1\text{B}$ to $\sim 530\text{M}$ parameters.

3.5 Adaptive Attention with Expert Routing

Earlier experiments applied expert routing only to FFN layers. For the pretrained-model setting we extend routing to the attention projections (W_Q, W_K, W_V, W_O), each decomposed into the same low-rank product structure. A single router per attention layer selects an expert at window granularity, and the same clone/prune lifecycle applies.

Empirically, attention and FFN layers exhibit different adaptation dynamics: FFN layers tend to remain at fewer experts (2–3), encoding stable domain knowledge in weight combinations, while attention layers grow to more experts (5–6), reflecting greater diversity in long-range pattern matching across domains. This asymmetry motivates separate gradient-threshold parameters for the two layer types (§3.6).

3.6 Per-Layer Gradient-Norm Clone Triggering

A natural starting point for the clone trigger is to compare the current loss to its exponential moving average and clone when the ratio exceeds a multiplicative threshold. Such a global loss-spike trigger fires the cloning event when *some* layer is cloned but gives no information about *which*—it conflates the *whether* of cloning with *where* to clone, and at the pretrained-model

scale we work with, the wrong layer is the common case. We replace it with a per-layer metric based on expert key gradients.

After each backward pass, for each adaptive layer ℓ with active expert set \mathcal{A}_ℓ , we compute:

$$g_\ell = \max_{s \in \mathcal{A}_\ell} \|\nabla_{k_s} \mathcal{L}\|_2 \quad (7)$$

where k_s is expert s 's key vector. A large g_ℓ indicates that the router is under pressure to redirect tokens away from the current expert allocation—a signal that the layer's existing experts are insufficient for the current distribution. Cloning is triggered when g_ℓ exceeds a threshold τ_ℓ that scales with the layer's capacity utilization:

$$\tau_\ell = \tau_{\text{base}} \cdot c(\text{fill}_\ell), \quad c(f) = \begin{cases} 1 & f \leq 0.5 \\ e^{\gamma t / (1-t)} & f > 0.5, \quad t = \frac{f-0.5}{0.5} \\ \infty & f \geq 1.0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where fill_ℓ is the fraction of expert slots currently active and γ controls how steeply the threshold rises as capacity fills (we use $\gamma=3$). This soft capacity limit allows free cloning when utilization is low but makes it exponentially harder near saturation.

Separate base thresholds τ_{attn} and τ_{fn} accommodate the different gradient scales and adaptation rates of the two layer types.

3.7 Null-Logit Routing

With gradient-norm clone triggering, every layer must produce meaningful key gradients—including layers that currently have only one active expert. A naïve softmax over a single logit always outputs 1.0, yielding zero gradient ($\partial \text{softmax}(x) / \partial x = 0$ when there is only one input). This would prevent single-expert layers from ever triggering a clone.

We resolve this with a **null logit** (fixed at zero) that appears in the backward pass only. Forward selection picks deterministically among real experts; the soft distribution that gradients flow through includes the null channel. Concretely, with N active experts and logits $\ell = (\ell_1, \dots, \ell_N)$:

$$e^* = \arg \max_{e \in [1, N]} \ell_e \quad (\text{forward: hard one-hot over real experts}) \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{w}_e = \text{softmax}([\ell_1, \dots, \ell_N, 0])_e \quad (\text{backward: soft, includes null}) \quad (10)$$

The forward routing weight is $w_{e^*} = 1$, $w_{e \neq e^*} = 0$, i.e. a hard one-hot over the highest-logit *real* expert. The backward gradient flows as if w were the soft real-expert distribution \tilde{w}_e for $e \in [1, N]$, with the null channel absorbing whatever softmax mass the bare distribution would have placed on it. Implementation uses a straight-through estimator: $w = w_{\text{hard}} + (\tilde{w} - \text{detach}(\tilde{w}))$.

For a single active expert with logit x and the null logit at zero: $\tilde{w}_1 = \sigma(x) = e^x / (e^x + 1)$, so $\partial \tilde{w}_1 / \partial x = \sigma(x)(1 - \sigma(x)) > 0$. The single-expert key receives non-zero gradient, allowing the spike trigger to fire and clone the expert when its loss is anomalously high. For multi-expert layers, the null channel keeps the soft distribution finite even when one logit dominates, smoothing the gradient signal on the keys without affecting which expert handles each window.

The hard-forward / soft-backward split is essential. An earlier implementation used `gumbel_softmax(hard=True)` over real experts plus null—which, by the straight-through semantics of `hard=True`, made the null channel a candidate output of the forward argmax. When null won, the routed branch produced zero output for that window, suppressing both the factor gradients and the spike-trigger signal that should drive cloning on out-of-distribution input. The corrected formulation above keeps null's gradient-flow benefit while ensuring every window contributes to the forward computation through some real expert.

4 Experiments

We evaluate RVW as an online adaptation method for a pretrained transformer. The base model is TinyLlama-1.1B; the test is online adaptation on a 6-domain interleaved random stream against four parameter-efficient and full-fine-tuning baselines, on both the matched decomposed base and the uncompressed pretrained model.

4.1 Pretrained Model Decomposition (TinyLlama-1.1B)

We apply the full RVW pipeline to TinyLlama-1.1B [17], a pretrained LLaMA-architecture model with 22 transformer layers, 2048 model dimension, and 5632 FFN dimension.

4.1.1 Setup

Decomposition. All 22 SwiGLU FFN layers are decomposed via truncated SVD at rank $r = 256$ with $L = 3$ factor matrices, as described in §3.4. Attention Q/K/V/O projections are similarly decomposed. The resulting model has ~ 530 M parameters (vs. 1.1B original).

Recovery fine-tuning. The decomposed model is fine-tuned on WikiText-103 to close the SVD approximation gap. Only FFN factor chains and attention projections are trained; the original attention head structure is preserved. We use a small learning rate and brief training to avoid overwriting pretrained knowledge.

Adaptive conversion. Each decomposed layer is converted to adaptive form: a single initial expert (copying the recovered weights), a router with learned key vectors, and empty slots for future clones. Expert routing uses null-logit softmax (§3.7) for all layers.

Online adaptation. The model is adapted on an interleaved 6-domain random stream of 15,000 chunks: WikiText (in-domain), Gutenberg English literature, FineWeb web text, FreeLaw legal opinions, The Stack code, and ArXiv scientific papers. At each step a domain is selected uniformly at random, so the model sees unpredictable distribution switches (~ 43 domain transitions in a typical run). Per-layer gradient-norm clone triggering (§3.6) with separate attention/FFN thresholds is used as the trigger throughout. Usage-based pruning occurs every 300 steps.

Hyperparameter optimization. Clone thresholds are optimized via coordinate-descent sweep: one parameter is varied at a time while others are held fixed. The scoring metric is the least-squares slope of eval PPL over time (normalized by initial baseline), with average final PPL as tiebreaker.

4.1.2 Coordinate-Descent Threshold Sweep

The sweep optimizes τ_{attn} and τ_{ffn} independently. Key findings from early sweeps:

- **Less cloning is better.** Higher thresholds (fewer clones) consistently produce lower final PPL. Runs with ~ 130 total clones outperform those with ~ 400 clones.
- **Asymmetric growth.** Early sweeps (with different threshold settings) showed attention layers growing to 5–6 experts while FFN layers stabilized at 2. With optimized thresholds, the pattern reverses: FFN layers grow more (mean 2.14, max 3 at end-of-run) while attention does not trigger clones at the chosen threshold. The direction of asymmetry depends on relative threshold values.

The combinatorial routing space is large even with restrained cloning. In our run, FFN layers reached up to 6 experts mid-stream before pruning settled them at a mean of 2.14 (max 3 at end-of-run); attention layers stayed at 1. With FFN layers averaging 2 active experts across 22 layers, $2^{22} \approx 4 \times 10^6$ unique routing patterns suffice to encode domain-specific behaviors, suggesting that individual expert specialization is not what distinguishes domains—the routing pattern is.

4.1.3 Results

Table 1 presents average held-out perplexity across all 15,000 chunks for each method. We evaluate two groups of baselines: methods operating on the *same decomposed base* ($\sim 530\text{M}$ parameters) as RVW, providing an apples-to-apples comparison of adaptation strategies, and methods on the *full uncompressed TinyLlama-1.1B*, providing a reference for the cost of compression.

Table 1: TinyLlama-1.1B average held-out perplexity on 6-domain random stream (15,000 chunks, lower = better)

Method	Base	Avg PPL
RVW (ours)	Decomposed 530M	40
Decomposed EWC ($\lambda=500$)	Decomposed 530M	158
Decomposed fine-tune	Decomposed 530M	164
Decomposed LoRA (rank-16)	Decomposed 530M	448
Decomposed frozen	Decomposed 530M	4,446
LoRA (rank-16)	Full 1.1B	7.8
Frozen	Full 1.1B	9.4
Full fine-tune	Full 1.1B	10,572
Full EWC ($\lambda=500$)	Full 1.1B	27,669

On the matched decomposed base, RVW achieves the lowest perplexity (40), outperforming decomposed EWC (158, $4.0\times$), decomposed fine-tune (164, $4.1\times$), decomposed LoRA (448, $11\times$), and decomposed frozen (4,446, $111\times$).

The full-model baselines show a striking asymmetry: LoRA on the uncompressed model achieves 7.8 PPL—essentially matching the frozen pretrained model (9.4)—because LoRA’s small adapters cannot meaningfully alter the pretrained weights. Full fine-tuning (10,572) and full EWC (27,669) both diverge sharply on this long 6-domain stream, suggesting that unrestricted weight updates overwrite pretrained knowledge faster than Fisher regularization can restrain.

Table 2 breaks down the results by domain for the decomposed-base methods.

Table 2: TinyLlama-1.1B per-domain mean PPL (decomposed-base methods only)

Method	Wiki	Guten	FineWeb	Legal	Code	ArXiv
RVW	22	7	97	24	59	31
Dec. EWC	181	31	304	64	178	89
Dec. FT	194	32	311	67	200	88
Dec. LoRA	455	96	617	267	809	501
Dec. Frozen	3,179	1,456	4,297	3,662	11,243	6,888

RVW outperforms all other decomposed-base methods on every domain. The largest absolute improvements are on Code (59 vs. 178, $3.0\times$) and FineWeb (97 vs. 304, $3.1\times$); the largest

Figure 2: Domain-switch recovery on the 6-domain random stream (matched 530M decomposed base, single seed). The stream is *blocked*: each domain is trained for a run of consecutive chunks before the stream switches, so a domain typically returns several times across the run. *Left*: held-out PPL on the first chunk when a domain *returns* after an absence—retention while away—against stream position, with per-method log-space trend lines. RVW retains a returning domain $\sim 12\times$ better than the parameter-matched baselines (geometric-mean cold re-entry 39 vs. 454–594). The baselines’ descending trend is underfitting recovery, not retention: they begin catastrophic and crawl toward merely poor. *Right*: every trained method reaches a comparable floor *while training on* a domain (faded bars, median within-block minimum PPL), but fine-tuning and EWC lose 23–25 \times of that gain by the next visit (solid bars, cold re-entry) against 7.5 \times for RVW—catastrophic forgetting in the baselines, largely resisted by the clone/prune lifecycle. Single seed; per-domain return counts range 3–12, so the robust claim is the pooled 44-block aggregate, not per-domain slopes. Reconstructed from the per-step held-out evals by `scripts/analyze_switch_recovery.py`, validated exactly against the stored adaptive-run recovery records.

relative improvements are on Gutenberg (7 vs. 31, 4.4 \times) and ArXiv (31 vs. 89, 2.9 \times). On Gutenberg, RVW (mean 7 PPL) approaches the uncompressed Frozen full 1.1B baseline (3.7 PPL), suggesting the routing mechanism recovers a substantial fraction of the capacity that compression removed for that distribution.

Convergence behavior. Table 3 compares last-10-chunk perplexity per domain, measuring each method’s converged performance.

Table 3: TinyLlama-1.1B last-10-chunk PPL per domain (convergence quality)

Method	Wiki	Guten	FineWeb	Legal	Code	ArXiv
RVW	10	10	97	13	38	13
Dec. EWC	66	33	255	27	102	26
Dec. FT	64	32	302	32	80	27

RVW converges to lower perplexity than EWC and fine-tuning on all 6 domains, with the largest gaps on the in-domain WikiText (10 vs. 66/64) and Gutenberg (10 vs. 33/32) end-state PPLs. This is consistent with the adaptive routing mechanism doing more than reducing initial shock—the ongoing maintenance of domain-specific expert configurations appears to also improve converged quality.

Retention across domain switches. The averaged and last-10 tables above conflate two distinct abilities: how well a method *fits* a domain while training on it, and how much it *retains* once the stream moves on and the domain later returns. Because the random stream is blocked—each domain is trained for a run of consecutive chunks before the stream switches to another—we can separate the two by measuring held-out PPL on the first chunk each time a domain *returns* after an absence, before any re-adaptation. This *cold re-entry* PPL is the genuine continual-learning signal that the averaged tables miss. Figure 2 reports it for all decomposed-base methods at the shared re-entry points (all methods see the same stream and the same switch sequence). Two readings stand out. First, all four trained methods reach a comparable floor *while training on* a domain—median within-block minimum PPL of 5 for RVW, 19–20 for fine-tuning and EWC, 55 for LoRA—so the ability to fit a domain is not the discriminator. Second, what survives the absence is: RVW’s geometric-mean cold re-entry is 39 PPL, against 454 (fine-tune), 459 (EWC), and 594 (LoRA), an $\sim 12\times$ retention gap. Equivalently, fine-tuning and EWC discard 23–25 \times of their in-block gain by the next visit while RVW discards 7.5 \times . The baselines’ *apparent* improvement over the stream—their cold re-entry falls across successive returns—is underfitting recovery rather than retention: they begin catastrophic and crawl toward merely poor as they slowly fit the compressed base, whereas RVW begins near its floor and stays there. We read the gap as direct evidence that the clone/prune lifecycle preserves domain-specific routing across absence rather than overwriting it—the dynamics counterpart to the combinatorial-encoding reading of §5.3. The claim is a retention *level* pooled over 44 switch blocks, not a per-domain trend: on a single seed, RVW’s own cold re-entry drifts modestly upward on some domains (WikiText, Gutenberg) while falling on others (ArXiv, FineWeb), so the lifecycle bounds forgetting rather than eliminating it.

Expert growth. Over 15,000 chunks, the model grows from 1 expert per layer to a total of 69 experts across 44 adaptive layers (22 attention + 22 FFN). FFN layers grow modestly (mean 2.14 experts, max 3); all 22 attention layers end at the single initial expert at the threshold values used here ($\tau_{\text{attn}}=0.45$). FFN layers reached as many as 6 experts during the run before pruning brought them back; attention layers never triggered a clone above the chosen threshold. This is consistent with the conjecture that attention patterns generalize better across domains at the 1B scale than the FFN projections that encode domain-specific knowledge, though the result also depends on the (hand-tuned) attention threshold and should be revisited with the spike-gated trigger introduced in subsequent work.

5 Discussion

5.1 Window-Level Routing

Standard mixture-of-experts routes individual tokens to specialized sub-networks. The clone/prune setting solves a different problem. We do not need to know which expert is best for each token; we need to know which expert configuration suits the current *distribution*, since distribution shift is what motivates adding capacity in the first place. Window-level routing reflects this directly: it averages the hidden state over W consecutive tokens before scoring against per-expert keys, so the routing decision sees enough context to make a reliable domain assessment and is amortized over a whole window of tokens. The cost is a slight latency penalty per window; the benefit is that the router becomes a domain detector rather than a token classifier, and the expert keys can be a single learned vector per expert rather than a gating network.

5.2 The Clone/Prune Lifecycle

The combination of clone trigger and prune cadence creates an evolutionary dynamic. The TinyLlama threshold sweeps support a clear qualitative reading: *when* and *where* to clone

matter more than *how often*. Higher per-layer gradient-norm thresholds, which produce fewer but more selective clones, dominate lower thresholds with many clones; runs with ~ 130 total clones outperform runs with ~ 400 clones at otherwise matched settings. Too-frequent cloning fragments the expert pool into redundant noisy copies that the router cannot distinguish; too-infrequent cloning fails to add capacity when the current pool is genuinely inadequate. The per-layer trigger localizes the new capacity to where it is needed, and gradient-directed perturbation initializes the new expert one step in the descent direction of the triggering distribution—so cloning is not an undirected exploration step but a targeted insertion of a candidate expert that already partly matches what the router was struggling to handle.

5.3 Combinatorial Expert Encoding

The TinyLlama-1.1B threshold sweeps reveal an inverse correlation between clone count and final quality: fewer, more restrained clones consistently outperform aggressive cloning. This supports a **combinatorial encoding** hypothesis: domain knowledge is not stored in individual specialized experts, but in the *routing pattern* across layers.

Consider a model with E experts per layer and L layers. Per-token routing, the model selects one expert per layer, yielding E^L possible configurations. Even with conservative expert counts ($E = 2$ across 22 layers), the 4×10^6 unique patterns vastly exceed the number of domains. Aggressive cloning that creates many narrowly-specialized experts actually *reduces* the effective routing diversity by fragmenting the expert space into overlapping specialists.

This has implications for clone/prune design: the system should create new experts sparingly, allowing routing to encode domain information in combinations of existing experts before resorting to capacity expansion.

5.4 Evolutionary Selection Pressure

Multi-cycle domain adaptation reveals an evolutionary dynamic in the expert pool. When the model is repeatedly exposed to domain switches (e.g., legal \rightarrow recovery cycles), experts that survive pruning across multiple shifts are inherently more general: they were useful enough in each domain to avoid being aged out. Over successive cycles, the expert population converges toward generalists—not because any explicit regularization encourages generality, but because the clone/prune lifecycle applies selection pressure favoring experts that contribute across distributions.

5.5 FFN–Attention Asymmetry

The TinyLlama-1.1B sweeps reveal a consistent asymmetry between FFN and attention layers, but in the opposite direction from early sweep predictions. With optimized thresholds ($\tau_{\text{attn}} = 0.45$, $\tau_{\text{ffn}} = 0.005$), FFN layers grow modestly (mean 2.14 experts, max 3 at end-of-run; up to 6 mid-run before prune) while attention layers never trigger clones at the chosen threshold. This suggests that at the 1B pretrained scale, attention patterns generalize well across domains (perhaps because the pretrained model has already learned robust attention heads), while FFN projections encode domain-specific knowledge that requires routing diversity. The much lower FFN threshold (0.005 vs. 0.45) reflects the larger gradient scale in FFN layers. Separate thresholds accommodate this asymmetry.

5.6 Limitations

- Truncated-SVD decomposition introduces an approximation gap relative to the original pretrained weights that must be closed by recovery fine-tuning before adaptation begins. The size of this gap depends on rank, factor count, and the quality of the recovery data.

- Per-layer gradient-norm thresholds were chosen by a coordinate-descent sweep, and the values τ_{attn} and τ_{ffn} may shift with model scale; we do not yet have a scale-invariant trigger.
- Window-level routing adds latency from the per-window mean computation and expert selection. The exact latency cost depends on W and the implementation; we have not yet optimized it (e.g., batched window routing, fused implementations).
- The pretrained-model evaluation uses 6 English-language domains and one base model (TinyLlama-1.1B). Multilingual adaptation, more extreme modality shifts, and different base architectures (e.g., hybrid SSM-attention) remain unexplored here.

5.7 Future Directions

- **Scale-invariant clone triggering.** A self-leveling trigger (e.g., based on the ratio of fast and slow EMAs of the gradient norm) could eliminate the coordinate-descent sweep on τ_{attn} and τ_{ffn} and allow attention and FFN to share a single multiplier.
- **External benchmarks.** Formal evaluation on continual learning benchmarks such as TRACE would provide standardized comparison with existing methods.
- **Larger and hybrid base models.** Extending the SVD decomposition to larger pretrained models, including hybrid SSM-attention architectures, would test whether the clone/prune lifecycle generalizes beyond pure-transformer targets.
- **Longitudinal regime-change studies.** The 15,000-chunk stream in the pretrained-model setting holds the domain set fixed throughout. Extending to runs that add and remove domains across stages would probe how the clone/prune lifecycle handles compositional regime change.
- **Chat and instruction following.** The decomposed 1.1B-parameter model has not yet been evaluated qualitatively on conversational tasks. Inference-time optimization (KV-cache, batched window routing) is also needed to make extended interactive use practical.

6 Conclusion

We presented RVW: a transformer architecture that supports a small pool of factor-chain experts per FFN and attention projection, with a per-layer gradient-norm clone trigger, gradient-directed clone perturbation, and usage-based pruning. Low-rank product factorization is the enabling substrate that makes the expert pool affordable, not the contribution: it lets a pool of K cloned experts share the heavy projections and differ only in the small factor chain, keeping the active-parameter cost close to that of a single dense projection.

Applied to TinyLlama-1.1B via truncated-SVD decomposition into a $5.3\times$ -compressed base ($\sim 530\text{M}$ parameters), RVW reaches 40 average PPL on a 15,000-chunk 6-domain stream. On the same decomposed base, EWC reaches 158, fine-tuning 164, and LoRA 448; on the uncompressed 1.1B model, full fine-tuning (10,572) and full EWC (27,669) both diverge sharply on the same long stream. Across all six domains evaluated, RVW outperforms every other adaptation method on the matched decomposed base. Per-layer gradient-norm clone triggering with null-logit routing provides a unified mechanism for both FFN and attention layers regardless of current expert count.

The TinyLlama threshold sweeps support a **combinatorial encoding** reading: domain knowledge appears to be carried by routing patterns across layers rather than by individual specialized experts, and fewer, more selective clones consistently outperform aggressive cloning.

We note this is a hypothesis supported by the inverse correlation of clone count and final quality, not a direct measurement of where knowledge is stored.

The clone/prune lifecycle is structurally analogous to the sleep-wake cycle in biological neural systems: waking plasticity (cloning) and sleep consolidation (pruning) interleave to form new connections while removing weak ones. The combination provides a parameter-efficient mechanism for continual adaptation of pretrained models that, on the evaluation reported here, outperforms existing parameter-efficient baselines on the same compressed base.

Reproducibility

All code, experimental scripts, and result files are available in the project repository.

TinyLlama-1.1B adaptation: TinyLlama-1.1B ($d=2048$, 22 layers, $d_{ff}=5632$, SwiGLU). SVD decomposition at rank $r=256$, $L=3$ factors for both FFN (gate/up/down) and attention (Q/K/V/O) projections. Recovery fine-tuned on WikiText-103. Adapted on 6-domain random stream (WikiText, Gutenberg, FineWeb, FreeLaw legal, The Stack code, ArXiv), 15,000 chunks with uniform random domain selection per chunk. Per-layer gradient-norm clone triggering with null-logit routing; $\tau_{\text{attn}}=0.45$, $\tau_{\text{ffn}}=0.005$. Baselines on decomposed base: fine-tune, EWC ($\lambda=500$), LoRA (rank-16, targeting q_down/q_up/v_down/v_up), frozen. Baselines on full 1.1B model: fine-tune, EWC, LoRA, frozen. Capacity exponent $\gamma=3$, usage decay 2.0, prune every 300 steps, adapt LR 1×10^{-4} . Run on Apple M4 Max (48GB), ~ 5 hours for the adaptive run.

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